

INFLUENCE OF ELASTIC ANISOTROPY ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS
OF CFRP COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An analytical solution of the stress intensity factor for a double edge notched (DEN) specimen is first presented by using the two dimensional isotropic elasticity theory. Some approximate expressions, which have been widely used for the determination of the stress intensity factor, are compared with this solution in order to check their accuracy. Secondly, the influence of elastic anisotropy on the stress intensity factor of an orthotropic DEN specimen is examined within the framework of the two dimensional anisotropic elasticity theory. Lastly, the fracture toughness of plain weave fabric carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is experimentally evaluated by taking into account their elastic anisotropy.

INTRODUCTION

Following the early work of Wu [1] many attempts to apply the linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) to fiber reinforced composite materials have been made in the last two decades. Such a LEFM approach is exclusively concerned with the determination of a stress intensity factor and a critical stress intensity factor, i.e., fracture toughness of notched materials. In most of these investigations [2-6] the critical stress intensity factor was determined using the LEFM formula for isotropic media.

However, in view of the fact that the fiber reinforced composite materials are generally anisotropic on a macroscopic level, it seems reasonable to evaluate the fracture toughness of such composites by taking

into account their elastic anisotropy [7]. It is the objective of this paper to determine the fracture toughness of plain weave fabric carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) by taking into account their elastic anisotropy. So we first present an analytical solution of the stress intensity factor for a double edge notched (DEN) specimen by using the two dimensional isotropic elasticity theory. Some approximate expressions, which have been widely used for the determination of the stress intensity factor, are compared with this solution in order to check their accuracy. Secondly, we consider this problem within the framework of the two dimensional anisotropic elasticity theory and show the influence of elastic anisotropy on the stress intensity factor of the orthotropic DEN specimen. Lastly, we evaluate the fracture toughness of the aforementioned CFRP composites by using the stress intensity factors obtained from these two elasticity theories and the experimentally determined fracture stresses.

STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR

A. Isotropic DEN Specimen

The Airy stress function for two edge dislocations at $(\pm \xi, 0)$ on the x-axis, having the Burgers vector by b , in an unbounded isotropic medium is given by [8]:

$$\chi = -\frac{2Gb_y}{\pi(\kappa+1)} (\gamma_1 \cdot \log \gamma_1 \cdot \cos \theta_1 - \gamma_2 \cdot \log \gamma_2 \cdot \cos \theta_2) \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. (a) Stress field due to two edge dislocations (b) DEN specimen and continuously distributed dislocations model.

In Eq.(1) G denotes the shear modulus and $K = 3-4\nu$ (plane strain) or $(3-\nu)/(1+\nu)$ (plane stress), where ν is Poisson's ratio. The polar coordinates r_i and θ_i are

$$\begin{aligned} r_1^2 &= (x-\xi)^2 + y^2, & r_2^2 &= (x+\xi)^2 + y^2 \\ \theta_1 &= \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{y}{x-\xi}\right), & \theta_2 &= \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{y}{x+\xi}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Now consider an elastic stress field due to two edge dislocations in an isotropic strip as shown in Figure 1(a). In this case the boundary conditions at free edges can be stated as

$$(\bar{\sigma}_x)_{x=\pm w/2} = (\bar{\tau}_{xy})_{x=\pm w/2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

and so the following stress function should be used in addition to Eq.(1):

$$\chi = \int_0^{\infty} g_1(\lambda) \cdot x \cdot \sinh(\lambda x) \cos(\lambda y) d\lambda + \int_0^{\infty} g_2(\lambda) \cdot \cosh(\lambda x) \cdot \cos(\lambda y) d\lambda \quad (4)$$

where $g_1(\lambda)$ and $g_2(\lambda)$ are unknown functions which are to be determined from the boundary conditions. By substituting the stress components $\bar{\sigma}_x$ and $\bar{\tau}_{xy}$ corresponding to Eqs.(1) and (4) into the boundary conditions of Eq.(3) and by applying the method of Fourier integral transforms to them, we have a system of simultaneous linear equations for the two unknown functions, from which all the unknowns are determined and the stress field due to the edge dislocations as shown in Figure 1(a) can be obtained. For later analysis, only the stress component in the y direction on the x -axis will be written here, that is

$$(\sigma_y)_{y=0} = -\frac{2Gby}{\pi(K+1)} \left\{ \frac{1}{x-\xi} - \frac{1}{x+\xi} + k(x, \xi) \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $k(x, \xi)$ is a function of x and ξ only.

With this result, we investigate a stress field of an isotropic DEN specimen under uniform tension away from the crack region, as shown in Figure 1(b). By continuously distributing an infinitesimal dislocation with density $f(\xi)$ from point A to B along the x -axis, as shown in Figure 1(b), and by using the superposition of the resulting stress and the uniform one together with a stress free condition on the crack surfaces, we have the following Cauchy-type singular integral equation of the first kind:

$$-\frac{2G}{\pi(K+1)} \int_{-w/2}^{w/2} \left\{ \frac{1}{x-\xi} - \frac{1}{x+\xi} + k(x, \xi) \right\} f(\xi) d\xi + \sigma = 0, \quad \left(\frac{w}{2} - c \leq x \leq \frac{w}{2} \right) \quad (6)$$

By making a change of variables such as

$$\xi = -\frac{c}{2} \cdot s + \frac{w-c}{2}, \quad x = -\frac{c}{2} \cdot t + \frac{w-c}{2} \quad (7)$$

Eq.(6) reduces to

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \left\{ \frac{1}{s-t} + \frac{1}{s+t-2(w-c)/c} + k^*(t, s) \right\} \phi(s) ds = 1, \quad (|t| \leq 1) \quad (8)$$

where $k^*(t,s)$ is a normalized kernel of $k(x,\xi)$ and $\phi(s)$ is an unknown function given by

$$\phi(s) = \frac{2G}{\sigma(K+1)} \cdot f\left(-\frac{c}{2} \cdot s + \frac{W-c}{2}\right) \quad (9)$$

The same equation as Eq.(8) was obtained by a different approach [9]. By solving Eq.(8) we can determine the unknown function $\phi(s)$, from which the stress field associated with Figure 1(b) is determined.

On the other hand, the stress intensity factor at the crack-tip point A is obtained as follows. Equation (8) with its right hand side replaced by $-(\sigma_y)_{y=0}/\sigma$ instead of unity holds for $|t|>1$ as well as $|t|\leq 1$ and, since the integral part with Cauchy kernel is dominant near the point A, it is approximated as

$$\frac{(\sigma_y)_{y=0}}{\sigma} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\phi(s)}{s-t} ds, \quad (t > 1) \quad (10)$$

Here, we assume the unknown function $\phi(s)$ to be

$$\phi(s) = F(s)/\sqrt{1-s^2} \quad (11)$$

where the new unknown function $F(s)$ is bounded and continuous in $|s|\leq 1$. By substituting Eq.(11) into Eq.(10) and using the mathematical formula we have

$$\frac{(\sigma_y)_{y=0}}{\sigma} \approx \frac{F(1)}{\sqrt{t-1}} \quad (12)$$

Then, by defining the stress intensity factor at the point A by

$$K_I = \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} \sqrt{\pi c(t-1)} \cdot (\sigma_y)_{y=0} \quad (13)$$

and substituting Eq.(12) into Eq.(13) we get

$$K_I/\sigma\sqrt{\pi c} = F(1) \quad (14)$$

B. Orthotropic DEN Specimen

The stress function for two edge dislocations at $(\pm\xi, 0)$ on the x-axis, having the Burgers vector by b , in an unbounded orthotropic medium is given by [10] :

$$\chi = -\frac{G_{xy} b y}{2\pi} \frac{(1+k_1)(1+k_2)}{(K_1-K_2)} \cdot \{ (\chi_{11} - \chi_{12}) - (\chi_{21} - \chi_{22}) \} \quad (15)$$

where, with $i=1$ and 2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{ii} &= \gamma_{ii} \cdot \log \gamma_{ii} \cdot \cos \theta_{ii} - \gamma_{ii} \cdot \theta_{ii} \cdot \sin \theta_{ii}, & \gamma_{ii}^2 &= \mu_i (x-\xi)^2 + y^2 \\ \chi_{2i} &= \gamma_{2i} \cdot \log \gamma_{2i} \cdot \cos \theta_{2i} - \gamma_{2i} \cdot \theta_{2i} \cdot \sin \theta_{2i}, & \gamma_{2i}^2 &= \mu_i (x+\xi)^2 + y^2 \\ \theta_{ii} &= \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{y}{\mu_i (x-\xi)} \right\}, & \theta_{2i} &= \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{y}{\mu_i (x+\xi)} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

In Eq.(15) G_{xy} denotes the shear modulus and, k_i and μ_i are constants depending on the elastic constants of the orthotropic medium. For the orthotropic strip with two edge dislocations as shown in Figure 1(a),

in addition to the above stress function, the following should be added in order to satisfy the free edge condition of Eq.(3):

$$\chi = \int_0^{\infty} g_1(\lambda) \cosh(\sqrt{\mu_1}\lambda x) \cos(\lambda y) d\lambda + \int_0^{\infty} g_2(\lambda) \cosh(\sqrt{\mu_2}\lambda x) \cos(\lambda y) d\lambda \quad (17)$$

where the unknown functions $g_1(\lambda)$ and $g_2(\lambda)$ are determined in the same procedure as in the isotropic case.

The stress component $(\sigma_y)_{y=0}$ thus obtained is given by

$$(\sigma_y)_{y=0} = -\frac{G_{xy} \cdot b_y}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{(1+k_1)(1+k_2)(\sqrt{\mu_1} - \sqrt{\mu_2})}{(k_1 - k_2)} \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{x-\xi} - \frac{1}{x+\xi} + k(x, \xi) \right\} \quad (18)$$

where the integral kernel $k(x, \xi)$ is a function of x , ξ , μ_1 and μ_2 .

Then, with this result, application of the method of continuous distribution of dislocations to the present orthotropic DEN specimen problem, as shown in Figure 1(b), leads to the same integral equation as Eq.(8) except for the kernel $k^*(t, s)$ being different in general, and also the stress intensity factor is determined from Eq.(14).

C. Numerical Results

It seems difficult to solve Eq.(8) analytically; so we substitute Eq.(11) into Eq.(8) and use the Lobatto-Jacobi integration rule [1] to obtain the numerical values of $F(s)$. The condition of $F(-1)=0$ is also used in order to obtain a single-valued solution. Table 1 and Figure 2 show the results for the normalized stress intensity factors $K_I/\sigma_1\sqrt{\pi c}$ calculated by

TABLE 1

Numerical results for the normalized stress intensity factors $K_I/\sigma_1\sqrt{\pi c}$

2C/W	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
(1)	1.000 (10.8)	1.004 (9.4)	1.016 (8.2)	1.040 (6.5)	1.075 (4.8)	1.128 (3.4)	1.208 (2.1)	1.336 (1.2)	1.565 (0.5)	2.133 (0.1)
(2)	1.120 (0.1)	1.130 (2.0)	1.128 (1.9)	1.125 (1.2)	1.132 (0.3)	1.164 (0.3)	1.228 (0.6)	1.338 (1.0)	1.504 (4.4)	1.740 (17.8)
(3)	1.122 (0.1)	1.124 (1.2)	1.129 (1.9)	1.141 (2.6)	1.163 (2.9)	1.201 (2.8)	1.264 (2.4)	1.375 (1.7)	1.588 (1.0)	2.123 (0.3)
(4)	1.122 (0.1)	1.121 (1.2)	1.118 (1.0)	1.120 (0.7)	1.132 (0.1)	1.163 (0.4)	1.226 (0.7)	1.343 (0.7)	1.567 (0.4)	2.113 (0.1)
(5)	1.122 (0.1)	1.122 (1.3)	1.124 (1.5)	1.131 (1.7)	1.149 (1.7)	1.184 (1.4)	1.247 (1.0)	1.359 (0.6)	1.577 (0.3)	2.118 (0.1)
Body force method	1.121 (0.0)	1.116 (0.7)	1.111 (0.3)	1.115 (0.3)	1.132 (0.2)	1.169 (0.1)	1.236 (0.1)	1.353 (0.1)	1.574 (0.1)	2.120 (0.1)
Present method	1.121	1.108	1.108	1.112	1.130	1.168	1.234	1.352	1.572	2.116

() : Accuracy (%)

Figure 2. Stress intensity factor as a function of crack-length.

the present method, the body force method [12] and some empirical formulas [13]. The empirical formulas used here are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad \frac{K_I}{\sigma \sqrt{\pi C}} &= \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi \zeta} \cdot \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \zeta\right)} \quad , \quad \text{with } \zeta = 2c/w \\
 (2) \quad \frac{K_I}{\sigma \sqrt{\pi C}} &= 1.12 + 0.203 \zeta - 1.197 \zeta^2 + 1.930 \zeta^3 \\
 (3) \quad \frac{K_I}{\sigma \sqrt{\pi C}} &= \frac{1.122 - 0.561 \zeta - 0.015 \zeta^2 + 0.091 \zeta^3}{\sqrt{1 - \zeta}} \quad (19) \\
 (4) \quad \frac{K_I}{\sigma \sqrt{\pi C}} &= (1 + 0.122 \cos^4\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \zeta\right)) \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi \zeta} \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \zeta\right)} \\
 (5) \quad \frac{K_I}{\sigma \sqrt{\pi C}} &= \frac{1.122 - 0.561 \zeta - 0.205 \zeta^2 + 0.471 \zeta^3 - 0.190 \zeta^4}{\sqrt{1 - \zeta}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3 Influence of elastic anisotropy on the stress intensity factor.

The results calculated by the empirical formulas (3), (4) and (5) have 3%, 1% and 2% accuracy compared to the present solution, while the results based on the body force method agree well with the present one with fairly good accuracy such that the difference can not be negligible in the Figure.

Figure 3 shows the influence of elastic anisotropy on the stress intensity factors. The results for the isotropic DEN specimen (Isotropy) are based on the present solution and the empirical formula (5). Those of the orthotropic DEN specimen are obtained from the present solution with $E_y/E_x=1$, $G_{xy}/E_x=0.0463$ and $\nu_{xy}=0.0495$ for Anisotropy (1), and $E_y/E_x=10$, $G_{xy}/E_x=0.0463$ and $\nu_{xy}=0.0495$ for Anisotropy (2). It is seen that the stress intensity factors taking into account the elastic anisotropy are smaller than the isotropic values and that, for the shorter crack-length, there

exists 10% difference at maximum between isotropic and anisotropic results.

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

A. Materials and Fabrication of DEN Specimen

The materials used were plain weave fabric carbon fiber prepregs (Torayca #6151B). The CFRP laminated composites were prepared by autoclave moulding and fabricated in the form of panels with $t=1\text{mm}$ and 1.95mm thick, from which the test specimens with 250mm long and 25mm wide were prepared.

The edge notches for DEN specimens, as shown in Figure 1(b), were cut with a handsaw and sharpened using a razoredge. Six different crack-lengths of DEN specimens were used in the investigations, $c=3.75\text{mm}$, 5mm , 5.5mm , 6.25mm , 7.5mm and 8.75mm which had notch depth to width ratios $2c/w$ of approximately 0.3, 0.4, 0.44, 0.5, 0.6 and 0.7, respectively.

B. Test Method

All tests were performed on an Instron TT-DM testing machine at a constant crosshead speed of $2\text{mm}/\text{min}$. The load-displacement curves of the CFRP specimens were found to be almost linear up to the maximum load with an abrupt brittle failure. This maximum load was therefore taken as the critical value.

C. Discussion

Following the results observed during testing, the critical fracture stress $\bar{\sigma} = P_{\text{max}}/wt$ is substituted into Eq.(14) together with isotropic and orthotropic values of $F(1)$ calculated in the previous section, then the critical stress intensity factor K_c , i.e., fracture toughness can be evaluated. The elastic constants used for the calculations of the orthotropic values of $F(1)$ are $E_x=E_y=66.30\text{ GPa}$, $G_{xy}=3.058\text{ GPa}$ and $\nu_{xy}=\nu_{yx}=0.049$, which were experimentally determined using uniaxial tensile tests for the same type CFRP specimens without notches as the DEN specimen. Figure 4 presents the fracture toughness K_c of CFRP composites thus obtained, which shows the influence of elastic anisotropy on the K_c values.

In this figure, \bigcirc and \bullet represent the fracture toughness which takes into account the elastic anisotropy of the CFRP composites or otherwise, respectively. We find that the values of the fracture toughness taking into account the elastic anisotropy are smaller than otherwise and that the influence of elastic anisotropy becomes more remarkable for the shorter crack-length.

Figure 4. Influence of elastic anisotropy on the fracture toughness K_c .

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The fracture toughness of CFRP laminated composites are evaluated by the double edge notched specimens (DEN) together with isotropic and anisotropic elasticity solutions for the stress intensity factors. In the course of the investigations, the accuracy of some empirical formulas, which have been widely used for the determination of the stress intensity factors of isotropic media, are also examined. The results thus obtained are summarized as follows:

- (1) The typical empirical formulas for the stress intensity factors of the isotropic DEN specimens have better than 3% accuracy compared to the present elasticity solutions.
- (2) The anisotropic (orthotropic) elasticity solutions give the smaller values of stress intensity factors than the isotropic counterparts.
- (3) The fracture toughness K_c evaluated by taking into account the elastic anisotropy of CFRP composites, i.e., by using the anisotropic elasticity solutions for the stress intensity factors, is smaller than otherwise, i.e., that evaluated by the isotropic elasticity solutions.
- (4) The influence of elastic anisotropy on the fracture toughness as mentioned above becomes more remarkable when evaluated using the DEN specimens with the shorter crack-length.

REFERENCES

1. Wu, E.M., Application of fracture mechanics to anisotropic plates. *J. Appl. Mech.*, 1967, 34, 967-74.
2. Waddoups, M.E., Eisenmann, J.R. and Kaminski, B.E., Microscopic fracture mechanics of advanced composite materials. *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1971, 5, 446-54.
3. Beaumont, P.W.R. and Phillips, D.C., Tensile strengths of notched composites. *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1972, 6, 32-46.
4. Owen, M.J. and Bishop, P.T., Critical stress intensity factors applied to glass reinforced polyester resin. *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1973, 7, 146-59.
5. Wright, M.A. and Iannuzzi, F.A., The application of the principles of linear elastic fracture mechanics to unidirectional fiber reinforced composite materials. *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1973, 7, 430-47.
6. Holdsworth, A.W., Owen, M.J. and Morris, S., Macroscopic fracture mechanics of glass reinforced polyester resin laminates. *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1974, 8, 117-29.
7. Kageyama, K., Nonaka, K., Shimamura, S. and Fukuda, S., Fracture toughness and acoustic emission of carbon-cloth/epoxy composites. *Trans. JSME (in Japanese)*, 1984, 50, 1260-66.
8. Dundurs, J., Elastic interaction of dislocations with inhomogeneities. *Mathematical Theory of Dislocations*, ed. T.Mura., ASME, 1969, pp.75.
9. Gupta, G.D. and Erdogan, F., The problem of edge cracks in an infinite strip. *J. Appl. Mech.*, 1974, 41, 1001-6.
10. Kasano, H., Watanabe, T. Matsumoto, H. and Nakahara, I., Stress intensity factors and order of stress singularities at the tips of a crack normal to the bimaterial interface. *JSME Int. J.*, 1987, 30,44-50.
11. Ioakimidis, N.I. and Theocaris, P.S., Numerical solution of Cauchy type singular integral equation by use of Lobatto-Jacobi numerical integration rule. *Appl. Matematiky*, 1978, 23, 439-52.
12. Nishitani, H., Preprint of JSME, (in Japanese), 1974, 155.
13. Tada, H., Paris, P.C. and Irwin, G.R., *The Stress Analysis of Cracks Handbook*, DEL Res. Corp., 1973, 2.7.